

WARNING: this list will not be anymore updated after this version

LIST OF THE ERA5 EVALUATION RUNS OF THE MED-CORDEX BASELINE RUNS

version 0: S. Somot, January 2022

version 1: S. Somot, April 2022, update after the Med-CORDEX workshop in Baseline runs

version 2: S. Somot, 26 Sept 2022, first official list, posted on zenodo

version 3: S. Somot, 12 mai 2023, various changes in preparation of the Med-CORDEX workshop

version 4: S. Somot, 1 Aug 2023, changes with the info from Med-CORDEX workshop, posted on zenodo

version 5: S. Somot, 3 May 2024, update (10 May 24, B. Ahrens -> GUF)

Version 6: S. Somot, 13 June 2024, changes after the Med-CORDEX workshop, posted on zenodo

Version 7: S. Somot, 20 April 2026, we stop using this list from now on to only rely on the official CORDEX simulation list,

<https://wcrp-cordex.github.io/simulation-status/>

In Med-CORDEX, 4 evaluation runs driven by ERA5 have been performed with 4 different RCSM configurations and by 4 different institutes.

Color Code: **Simulations done**, **Simulations planned or running**

Model Naming, <i>source_id</i>	Period	Status	<i>Last update</i>
CNRM-RCSM6B-SN	1980-2022	done	2024-05
ENEA-REG2	1980-2014	done	2023-05
ENEA-REG3	1970-2020	done	2026-04
CCLM5-0-9-NEMOMED12-3-6	1979-2022	done	2024-05
RegCM-ES1-1	1960-2020	running	2025-07

RegIPSLv2		planned	2023-05
LMDZ4-NEMOMED8v2	1979-2021	done	2024-01
MedESM		planned	2024-05
EBUPOM2e		planned	2023-05
ICON-OASIS-NEMO		planned	2024-05
MedX-CM	1979-2020	planned	2025-06

REFERENCES: